

xR Network+

Accelerating Innovation in Performing Arts

Reporting from the XR Network+
Royal Shakespeare Company Research
and Development Challenge

White Paper

Reporting from the XR Network+ Royal Shakespeare Company Research and Development Challenge

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Executive Summary

This paper outlines the process and outcomes of the XR Network+ Royal Shakespeare Company (RSC) Research and Development (R&D) Challenge. It also explores the additional, critical value provided by the XR Stories team at the University of York, who lead the XR Network+ project and act as an expert intermediary and connection point between all key project stakeholders as part of a managed innovation process.

Commencing in 2024, the R&D Challenge provided an opportunity for academic-led projects to apply for funding to deliver innovative R&D projects to tackle an industry-led challenge co-designed by XR Network+ and the RSC.

The role of the expert intermediary in this collaborative R&D context is to accelerate research, development and innovation processes that strategically combine cultural partners and university research teams to solve industry-wide challenges.

Operating as the intermediary, XR Stories aims to shorten the time-to-impact for new creative technologies and workflows by co-designing industry R&D challenges, supporting high-quality project proposals, and aligning artistic intent, research capability, and industry practice.

The model de-risks innovation by bridging translation gaps, providing crucial cross-sector facilitation, and generating internal value for the intermediary while delivering tangible R&D outcomes.

Image: On stage at The Swan theatre, in between performances and with working lights.

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1. Context: XR Network+, XR Stories and intermediation in the creative economy

XR Network+ is a five-year, £3.3m Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)-funded project dedicated to establishing a ten-year research agenda for Virtual Production (VP) / Extended Reality (XR) content creation and consumption in the UK digital economy. XR Network+ is led by the XR Stories team at the University of York in collaboration with the University of Edinburgh, University of the Arts London, Cardiff University and Ulster University.

Research collaboration, co-creation and challenge-led innovation are the cornerstones of XR Network+ activity (Willment, N., Murphy, D., Black, S., Mothersdale, G., Harris, J., & Terras, M. (2024). The project is building a community of academic research and industry (R&D) at the convergence of ideas, technologies, and creative practice in VP to deliver impact and opportunity, not just for the creative industries, but for the whole of the digital economy.

Roles of intermediation are under-theorised in the creative industries, particularly concerning R&D activities bringing

together creative practice and technological advancement. The R&D process in the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) is often enhanced by key intermediaries performing multiple processes simultaneously, combining aspects of cultural intermediation with innovation management.

2. The Royal Shakespeare Company R&D Challenge

The value of XR Stories as an expert intermediary is evident in its work co-designing R&D challenges that precisely target the creative and operational needs of its partners. The RSC R&D Challenge serves as a key example of this process, where the XR Stories team supported the RSC to frame R&D opportunities around specific, defined industry problems.

XR Stories has deployed similar approaches to challenge partnerships with Warner Bros Discovery, ITV, Sky, and the Science Museum Group, as a form of Managed Innovation (MI): de-risked agile R&D programmes offering partners strategic innovation opportunities by matching them with innovative small companies and leading academic researchers.

Actor Matthew Churcher and Davi Callanan, Director and Video Designer, on a performance shoot. Photo by Michelle Wu, CAMERA

2.1 Defining the technical scope of the R&D Challenge

The R&D Challenge was specifically co-designed by XR Stories and the RSC to enable two project teams to work with the RSC to explore how VP technologies could contribute to live performance and provide new theatre experiences for audiences across various platforms.

The co-design process focused on identifying technological innovations in the form of tools, workflows and pipelines, rather than seeking new creative content. This focus ensured that the funded research, enabled via XR Network+, would directly address practical technical constraints encountered in a major cultural institution.

The resulting brief specified four primary areas for innovation:

- 1 Developing tools for real-time performance capture capable of operating under dynamic 'stage conditions'.
- 2 Creating workflows that allow real-time performance data to drive on stage video/3D assets.
- 3 Establishing pipelines for using real-time performance data to drive dynamic and free moving objects.
- 4 Exploring methods for using real-time facial capture data to map to tactile, moving surfaces.

The brief also identified performer and creative-led uses of real time technologies as a broader area for innovation.

2.2 Roles and responsibilities

The co-design approach defined clear roles for both partners during the project lifecycle:

The RSC committed to providing creative and strategic direction to the projects and maximising opportunities for engagement with the wider RSC organisation. The RSC also committed to attending fortnightly project progress meetings.

XR Stories assumed the expert intermediary role, offering support with day-to-day communication between the projects and the RSC, supporting project delivery, and promoting the research outputs.

The open-call challenge application process included a structured co-design/refinement phase. Following an initial shortlisting process where applications were assessed by independent reviewers, the XR Stories team, the RSC, and successful first-stage applicant teams were invited to a half day session at the RSC in Stratford-upon-Avon. This enabled the short-listed researchers to refine their proposals in direct dialogue with the RSC and ensured that the final two projects selected were strategically aligned with the theatre company's practical and creative needs.

2.3 Thinking through Intellectual Property (IP)

Bringing valuable solutions to market is one of the key success measures of R&D. The co-design approach integrated a workable strategy for commercialising successful outcomes, based on the knowledge and practice developed by the XR Stories team and wider Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) Creative Industries Clusters programme practice.

While new IP created by the projects was wholly owned by the awarded project teams, the agreement granted the RSC a one-year period beyond the end of each project to agree terms for further development and exploitation of the project outputs.

This structural alignment ensures that the challenge partner (the RSC), having shaped the R&D requirements, and contributed to the development of the projects' intellectual property, has a direct path to integrating the resulting innovations into their activities.

Akhila Krishnan, Creative Director and Video Designer, RSC Interdisciplinary Fellow 2024 - 2025, and Davi Callanan, Director and Video Designer, performing technical checks on motion capture sound and lighting. Photo by Michelle Wu, CAMERA

Actor Matthew Churcher pre-performance for a motion capture shoot.
Photo by Michelle Wu, CAMERA.

3. Applications to the XR Network+ RSC Challenge: Synthesis of key themes

This section synthesises the core technical and creative themes identified across the 16 project applications submitted to the XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge. The proposals demonstrated strong interest in moving Virtual Production (VP) and Extended Reality (XR) from technical systems toward tools that enhance the artistic nuance, accessibility, and audience reach of live performance.

3.1 Performance nuance and human fidelity

A dominant theme across the submissions was the recognition that existing motion capture (mocap) technology fails to capture the subtle, authentic elements critical to live acting, leading to robotic or wooden digital characters. Projects focused on bridging this emotional and physiological gap:

Biodata integration:

Multiple project proposals aimed to incorporate physiological data beyond basic skeletal movement including: integrating biodata (heart rate, breathing, skin conductivity, and neuro-behaviour) using an Open Sound Control (OSC)¹ pipeline to drive dynamic changes in avatar characteristics, capturing involuntary, and intuitive details of performance.

Capturing breath and soft tissue:

One project application focused specifically on capturing, analysing, and rendering the actor's breathing behaviour in real time, noting that breath conveys vital information about physical and emotional state that is currently lost in skeletal-based rendering. Another project sought to develop hybrid reality capture (mocap + volumetric capture) to preserve the nuance of live performance, such as breath patterns and muscle tension.

Enhanced optical capture:

One project aimed to overcome limitations of traditional optical mocap by using smaller, more discreet 5mm markers alongside 5K cameras to track non-rigid and non-skeletal motion, empowering performers to control additional digital elements of a performance in real-time.

3.2 Democratic and accessible workflows

Several applications focused on reducing the technological and financial barriers associated with high-end VP equipment, thereby democratising access for creative practitioners and expanding the use of XR beyond large institutional venues:

Markerless and low-cost systems:

One proposal aimed to demonstrate a pipeline for markerless performance capture using accessible consumer hardware (off-the-shelf cameras and gaming PCs), seeking solutions that are flexible, scalable, and tourable. Another project highlighted the potential for [Move.ai](https://www.move.ai/)'s markerless technology² to eliminate the need for costly suit-based alternatives, anticipating that such technology will soon be accessible enough for a Gen Alpha³ bedroom.

Tools for non-programmers:

One project proposed creating a multi-modal toolset based on [Unreal Engine](https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US)⁴ that enables non-programmers to design modular systems for performance space control, responding directly to the need for wider accessibility.

Portable control systems:

One project proposed a system designed to enable portable, plug-and-play access to immersive special effects using common communication protocols such as OSC, offering a low-cost, sustainable model for both large and small production companies.

¹ Open Sound Control (OSC) is a protocol for networking sound synthesizers, computers, and other multimedia devices for purposes such as musical performance or show control.

² <https://www.move.ai/>

³ People born from approximately 2010 to 2024 and is characterized by being the first generation born entirely within the 21st century

⁴ <https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US>

LX and SD motion capture loaded performance cues. Photo by Michelle Wu, CAMERA

3.3 Multi-platform distribution and remote audienceship

The R&D Challenge application guidance specified the RSC's ambition to become a multi-platform theatre company, focusing on how to distribute live performance content from the stage across new digital channels, and moving beyond traditional screen viewing. A number of proposals aligned with this goal:

Virtual twins and touring models:

One project proposed creating a framework for 'virtual twins' of stage productions, for rehearsing shows and hosting live online performances, replicating the spatial experience of theatre.

Engaging Generation Z via gaming platforms:

One project aimed to directly target younger audiences (Gen Z) by exploring a novel distribution model within Fortnite, creating virtual venues and 'as live' performances on a custom Fortnite Island. Another project noted the potential for recorded performances to be installed as 'islands' in Fortnite.

HMD enhancements and hybrid experiences:

Multiple projects explored viewing through Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs). One project sought to define the production workflow for content distributed concurrently to traditional screens and HMD viewers, focusing on the user impact of HMD enhancements. Another planned to develop pipelines for 5G streaming live digital performance to a remote audience experiencing it in Apple Vision Pro.

Actor training for XR:

One project wanted to explore the affordances of motion capture, HMDs, and virtual environment design for actor training, rehearsal, performance, and audienceship in XR theatre.

3.4 Simulation, optimisation, and AI-driven workflows

Some project applications wanted to explore real-time performance capture solutions that are technically reliable in unpredictable theatrical contexts, addressing the infrastructure required for testing and optimisation:

Simulation environments:

One project proposed creating a comprehensive simulation environment to optimise volumetric capture systems for live theatre. The tool would simulate and test various camera and sensor configurations within a detailed 3D digital model of a stage to ensure reliable real-time data collection under dynamic stage conditions.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) for co-creation and automation:

A project proposed integrating AI-driven agents that can co-act with performers and facilitate code-free generation of virtual objects, enhancing narrative and staging capabilities. Other projects proposed to embed machine learning models to synthesize and refine data streams, such as training an AI to enhance real-time motion capture data with the nuances of volumetric capture.

Tackling the Uncanny Valley:

Another project specifically framed its core challenge as tackling the Uncanny Valley⁵ in VP, proposing an Unreal Engine pipeline that combines real-time capture, Generative AI, and VP methods with the 'human touch' to create believable and emotionally engaging virtual beings.

⁵ A phenomenon where human-like objects, such as robots or CGI characters, evoke feelings of revulsion and unease in observers as they become almost, but not perfectly, realistic.

4. The RSC R&D Challenge Projects

Following the open call and peer review, two projects were commissioned:

1

Centre for the Analysis of Movement, Entertainment Research and Applications (CAMERA), University of Bath: Focusing on using real-time motion and audio data to pre-visualise acoustic and visual blocking.

2

Centre for Performance, Technology and Equity (PTEQ), Royal Central School of Speech and Drama: Focusing on accessible mixed-reality tools for rehearsal and stage management.

Interior photo of the Royal Shakespeare Theatre auditorium, taken with actors and audience at Builder's Opening Night. Photo by Peter Cook © The RSC

4.1 CAMERA, University of Bath

This case study examines the CAMERA (University of Bath) strand of the XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge. It focuses on the project's goals, technical approach, key outcomes, and challenges identified during the intensive research sprint.

Project overview and collaboration model

The R&D project, titled 'The Actor as an Engine: Incorporating virtual production tools to reinvent the stage', explored how real-time motion capture could be used as a control mechanism in live theatrical settings, integrating with stage lighting, video, and sound systems using artist-centred workflows.

The project exemplifies a strategic collaboration model as part of a Managed Innovation process: Creative Institution × Research Centre × Expert Intermediary.

Creative / cultural institution (RSC): Provided artistic vision, live performance testbeds, and access to world-leading theatre artists and technicians.	Research centre (CAMERA, University of Bath): Contributed advanced real-time technologies, mature expertise in optical motion capture, volumetric techniques, and research capability.	Expert intermediary (XR Stories, University of York): Curated the challenge, facilitated day-to-day integration, provided ethics/governance support, and translated learning across sectors for the XR Network+ project
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The project ran from March 2025 to July 2025, with an intensive time-boxed sprint between 4 July and 9 July 2025.

Core objectives and approach

The project set out to prototype a performer-driven control stack using theatre-ready workflows and minimal on-performer instrumentation. The core challenge, framed by the RSC, included exploring real-time performance capture under dynamic 'stage conditions' and using that data to drive on-stage video, 3D assets, and dynamic objects.

Key Technical Approaches

Component	Description	Rationale
Motion capture	Optical motion capture using a small number of rigid marker clusters attached to key body regions.	This minimised intrusion and allowed for marker disguise within a costume, a critical factor for theatre logistics and aesthetics.
Data pathways	Open Sound Control (OSC) data strings streamed to media servers and sent directly to the lighting desk using lightweight, event-based network messages.	Enabled direct control pathways, offering flexibility and exploring latency reduction.
Show systems	Integration with media servers for projection/video, the lighting desk for responsive states, and game engine and queuing software for a spatial audio proof-of-concept triggered by performer position.	Demonstrated multi-system control driven by a single motion source.
Calibration	Adopted an adaptive calibration approach to handle challenging stage conditions (haze, strong key light, partial occlusion).	Ensured system robustness in a dynamic, real-time environment.

Key outcomes and achievements

The R&D sprint resulted in a compact and convincing demonstration of performer real-time expressive control of light, image, and sound:

Real-time control:

Lighting and video reacted to performer actions (walks, crouches, gestures) with sub-second responsiveness.

Lean instrumentation:

The use of cluster-based tracking successfully reduced setup time and visual intrusion compared to full mocap suits.

Spatial audio prototyping:

A spatial audio test demonstrated that performer position within virtual zones on the stage could trigger layered sound effects.

Stage-credible workflows:

The team demonstrated that real-time data streams could operate alongside conventional cue stacks (e.g., using submasters and manual overrides) without destabilising show control to provide operational safety and resilience.

Rehearsal methodology:

An approach emerged that integrates creative iteration with technical reliability, including record-and-replay pipelines to prevent over-taxing the performer during technical iteration.

Constraints and open challenges

The constraints and challenges related to technology integration and workflow alignment:

Technical stability:

Tracking continuity suffered from occasional cluster drop-outs due to fast movement and occlusion. This was partially mitigated by designing unique, mirror-proof, non-coplanar marker cluster layouts but remained a challenge in the compressed development window.

System limitations:

Existing commercial show control systems, such as the lighting desk, provide limited filtering over incoming OSC data. This necessitated the development of a filter programme or hybrid interface to prevent system overload and enable creatives to control when data is sent.

Vocabulary gap:

A creative/technical vocabulary gap was evident, as lighting and video cueing norms differed significantly from real-time control paradigms, requiring the intermediary (XR Stories) to align expectations and facilitate communication.

Fine motion capture:

The lean instrumentation successfully captured large movements but was insufficient for detailed limb articulation or subtle expression, like fingers, breath, or muscle tension, suggesting a need for future R&D involving machine learning.

Value and future recommendations

The CAMERA project validated the Creative Institution × Engine × Expert Intermediary Managed Innovation model, demonstrating that performer-driven stage systems are feasible with current technology when research is co-designed with artists. Value was created across the following key areas:

Creative agency:

The work offers directors and performers agency over digital scenography, allowing gestures to author light, image, and sound.

Market portability:

The low on-body load and gesture-driven media make the outputs legible and attractive to adjacent sectors, including heritage/visitor experiences, healthcare and rehabilitation, and live events.

The project also made the following key recommendations:

Development of a hybrid routing and mapping tool that visualises the stage in 3D, filters and routes marker data, and presents cue/timeline logic familiar to lighting workflows.

The institutionalisation of pre-tech R&D sprints (e.g. four to six weeks ahead of technical rehearsal) to stabilise toolchains and establish gesture-effect grammars, thereby lowering risk in the main production phase.

4.2 PTEQ, Royal Central School of Speech and Drama

This case study examines the PTEQ project of the XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge. It focuses on the project’s goals, technical approach, key outcomes, and challenges identified during its research and development.

Project overview and collaboration model

The project, ‘Virtual Rehearsal Room’ investigated how virtual environments and digital twins could be integrated into established theatrical production processes to streamline workflows and empower artistic creativity.

<p>Creative / cultural institution (RSC): Provided artistic vision, live performance testbeds, and access to world-leading theatre artists and technicians.</p>	<p>Research centre (PTEQ, Royal Central School of Speech and Drama): Developed a prototype for a virtual rehearsal environment working in collaboration with technology developer Agile Lens, digital twin provider Preevue, and acoustic specialists Threshold.</p>	<p>Expert intermediary (XR Stories, University of York): Curated the challenge, facilitated day-to-day integration, provided ethics/governance support, and translated learning across sectors for the XR Network+ project.</p>
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Core objectives and approach

The primary objective was to prototype a working virtual rehearsal environment in Unreal Engine, including tools for actors, directors, and stage managers. The approach involved building a proof-of-concept using a high-fidelity digital twin of the RSC Swan Theatre and its stage designs.

Development focused on creating practical tools—such as a virtual script reader, spatial cubes, and blocking recorders—which were tested and iterated upon in workshops with RSC creative teams. A key finding was the identification of stage managers as a primary user group currently underserved by technology, which led to a refined focus on their specific needs.

Key technical approaches

Component	Description	Rationale
Virtual environment	High-fidelity digital twin of the RSC Swan Theatre and stage designs, built in Unreal Engine.	To provide a realistic, spatially accurate, and immersive environment for pre-production and remote rehearsal.
Blocking tools	Spatial cubes and blocking recorders (tools for digitising and automating the recording of blocking positions).	To streamline workflows for stage managers (identified as a key underserved user group) and facilitate real-time spatial planning.
Script reader	A virtual script reader tool integrated within the environment.	To allow actors and directors to reference the script digitally while working within the 3D space.
Core platform	A working virtual rehearsal environment prototype.	To empower artistic creativity and streamline established theatrical production processes through digital integration.

Investigating virtual environments and digital twins at the RSC.

Key outcomes and achievements

The project successfully delivered a stable prototype of the virtual rehearsal room. Key outcomes and achievements from the R&D included:

Validation of numerous high-value use cases, including remote understudy rehearsals, digital site visits for actors, and the ability for directors to explore sightlines from any seat in the house during pre-production.

An unexpected but significant outcome was the enthusiastic response from stage managers, who saw immediate practical benefits in tools that could digitise and automate the recording of blocking positions in real-time.

The research proved that hybrid physical-virtual rehearsals are effective and can lead to faster spatial planning and earlier cross-team collaboration.

Constraints and open challenges

The project faced several challenges common in creative R&D:

Script import workflow:

The complexity of a user-friendly script import workflow required the development of a custom tool to process text into a usable format.

Feature Prioritisation:

Due to limited time and resources, ambitious features like high-fidelity avatars and real-time prop tracking were deprioritised to focus on core functionality, though they remain on the future roadmap.

Acoustic Simulation:

Connecting live actor audio to the acoustic simulation proved more complex than anticipated, so the concept was validated using pre-recorded sounds instead.

Value and future recommendations

The project generated significant value by highlighting that the rehearsal process is a largely overlooked but ideal site for virtual production research and innovation. Value was created across the following key areas:

Accessibility and sustainability:

The project demonstrated workflows that could improve accessibility and economic and environmental sustainability for theatre companies of all sizes.

Market portability:

The outputs have clear portability to touring productions (for pre-visualising in new venues), actor training programmes, and remote creative development.

Key project recommendations:

The project team has identified that future funding could be used to develop the prototype into a deployable platform, prioritizing the refinement of the stage management tools and integration with standard theatre software such as QLab⁶ and Vectorworks⁷.

The project also underscored the need for open-source standards for script and blocking data to ensure wider adoption and interoperability.

⁶ <https://qlab.app/>

⁷ <https://www.vectorworks.net/en-GB>

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5. The intermediary role of XR Stories in practice

Research into Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) confirms that successful R&D relies on entities capable of navigating the distinct cognitive and operational domains of cultural, academic, and commercial sectors. As Stockley-Patel and Swords (2023) define, intermediation falls into two primary categories: **cultural intermediation** (focused on curation, consumption, and taste-making) and **innovation intermediation** (focused on translating technology and de-risking the innovation pathway).

The role of XR Stories in the RSC Challenge is firmly established as an **innovation intermediary**. This function is critical for bridging the acknowledged “translation gaps” between the cultural sector’s emphasis on artistic value and the technological sector’s focus on technical capability. The intermediary thus acts strategically as a **boundary spanner**; an entity capable of operating and translating knowledge across the distinct cognitive and operational domains of the arts and academia. By actively managing this knowledge flow, XR Stories de-risks the R&D process, ensuring that the research trajectory remains aligned with high-impact,

real-world utility, thereby accelerating the time-to-impact (Stockley-Patel & Swords, 2023; Taylor, 2015).

Previous analysis of this managed innovation model by XR Stories (Stockley Patel and Swords, 2023)⁸ also demonstrates a positive economic impact: companies involved in these rapid prototyping challenges consistently report **higher employment, higher revenue growth**, and the creation of **revenue-generating assets** when compared to non-Managed Innovation companies. Interestingly, while the Managed Innovation model is highly effective at accelerating growth, participating companies tended to perceive the intermediary role as one that sped up a process that would have occurred in any case.

This contrasts with companies who are not subject to a Managed Innovation process, but who often still credit XR Stories as being “extremely important” to their growth. This suggests that Managed Innovation projects engage more established companies or organisations who nonetheless achieve significant acceleration and valuable assets from the risk-free R&D framework that is enabled.

The success of the challenge was predicated on a defined collaborative model:

Challenge Holder / Cultural Institution (RSC):

Providing high-level strategic challenge, artistic intent, and real-world deployment context.

University:

Providing deep research and technical expertise, R&D methodology, and resources to build novel prototypes, working in partnership with key industry companies.

Expert Intermediary (XR Stories):

Bridging the gap through translation, project management, and strategic alignment, ensuring the outputs are technically robust, commercially viable, and artistically useful.

⁸ <https://xrstories.co.uk/publication/cultural-and-innovation-intermediation-in-the-cultural-creative-industries/>

To address the need for more practical contexts, the following sub-sections detail how XR Stories delivered its expert intermediary function during the RSC Challenge, demonstrating the 'how' of its value through deliberate boundary-spanning activities, and highlighting some of the challenges.

5.1 Co-designing the XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge

Activity:

Moving from broad industry needs to targeted, fundable R&D questions.

Example:

Planning a coherent R&D challenge, relevant to the RSC, the university-led teams designing the projects, and Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) working in collaboration with their lead University partners, required careful co-design. XR Stories facilitated a series of intensive scoping conversations with the RSC team to understand their immediate and longer term challenges and opportunities. This process narrowed the focus from general workflows to a focus on actor and creative-led rehearsal, production and live workflows. This targeted brief ensured commissioned projects would deliver outcomes with immediate utility, with benefits to the RSC and the wider industry.

Ongoing challenges: Both the [XR Network+ R&D themes](#)⁹ and the challenges and opportunities for the performing arts industry are broad. The R&D themes were articulated at the outset of the XR Network+ project and all applicants must identify how their project proposals align with at least one theme to be eligible for funding.

5.2 Facilitating cross-sector communication and collaboration

Activity:

Managing communication and working practices between different professional cultures (theatre, computer science, tech companies).

Example:

For the CAMERA (University of Bath) team, the artistic goals developed slowly over the initial stages of the project. For the PTEQ (Royal Central School of Speech and Drama) project, several industry partners were collaborating on technical elements of their prototype tool. XR Stories set up structured regular meetings and collaborative tools and templates to enable teams to share artistic/creative briefs and technical development, and to share knowledge between the two projects. Additionally, both projects culminated in intensive, multi-day R&D sprints, which enabled focused and purposeful collaboration, testing and iteration.

Ongoing challenges: All collaborative projects offer different combinations of skills and experience from the partners, and in the RSC Challenge projects, a mix of more and less mature collaborative relationships. Within project delivery windows and funding constraints, more time could have been allocated at the start to building those relationships.

5.3 Guiding IP strategy and commercialisation pathways

Activity:

Ensuring valuable project outputs have a viable path to future use and impact.

Example:

As R&D progressed, and custom tools and processes were created, XR Stories liaised with the project partners to understand the value of the IP being created. This guidance, provided early in the project lifecycle, explored where open source outputs or knowledge transfer from university researchers to industry professionals was appropriate. It also positioned the tools for potential wider adoption across the theatre and performance industries, maximising the public benefit of the EPSRC funding and creating a foundation for impact.

Ongoing challenges: Active support and encouraging open discussion notwithstanding, persistent challenges around IP and commercialisations exist in projects where collaborating partners include quasi-public institutions like universities (who may need to negotiate and balance competing pressures to open-sourcing or commercialising research and R&D activities) and industry partners developing commercial IP. In the RSC R&D Challenge, additional challenges related to a multi-national collaboration including several small companies based in the US. Additional care and attention when designing future R&D challenges will help mediate some of the complexity caused by more collaborative partner structures.

⁹ <https://xrnetworkplus.xrstories.co.uk/about/themes/>

6. Conclusions and stakeholder-specific recommendations

The XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge successfully demonstrated that the **Cultural Institution × Research Centre × Expert Intermediary** Managed Innovation model is highly effective at de-risking creative R&D and achieving high-quality, relevant outcomes. The intermediation role played by XR Stories was critical in achieving project alignment, translating cross-sector requirements, and guiding deployment strategy.

To build on this success, the following stakeholder-specific recommendations are proposed:

6.1 Recommendations for research funding bodies

Mandate intermediary roles:

Future large-scale, cross-sector funding calls should explicitly allocate budget and resources for an expert, dedicated intermediary function (as facilitated here by XR Stories) to manage the overall initiative and intermediate between industry and academia, arts and culture and technology, and small and large organisations.

Prioritise open standards in R&D:

Explore funding streams dedicated to the development of open-source standards and protocols to facilitate interoperability and ensure R&D outputs are not locked into proprietary systems, whilst not adversely affecting industry partners.

Support longitudinal development:

Allocate follow-up funding for the most promising prototypes, to bridge gaps between Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4 (validation in a lab environment) and TRL 7 (demonstration in an operational environment), ensuring stronger paths to viable commercialisation.

Investigating virtual environments and digital twins at the RSC.

6.2 Recommendations for industry-leading cultural institutions

Establish dedicated R&D capacity:

Cultural organisations should establish and maintain small, internal R&D teams, innovation practices, or designated Innovation Leads to work directly with intermediaries and R&D partners. This would improve the internal capability to absorb and implement R&D outputs.

Prioritise process R&D in XR technologies:

Move beyond a current focus on audience-facing technology. Actively champion R&D focused on improving internal production workflows (such as rehearsal, stage management, and sustainability) as demonstrated by the success of the XR Network+ RSC R&D Challenge.

6.3 Recommendations for creative R&D teams and universities

Plan for open-source first:

Adopt a default strategy of using permissive open-source licenses for R&D outputs where appropriate. This accelerates adoption by SMEs and other cultural institutions, fulfilling the remit of public funding.

Prioritise User Experience (UX) in creative contexts:

Ensure the technical development plan includes significant time and budget for UX design, often in collaboration with the intermediary, to ensure artistic accessibility and utility for creative professionals.

Investigating virtual environments at the Centre for Performance, Technology and Equity, Royal Central School of Speech and Drama.

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